

Development and Evaluation Hydrogel of SertaconazoleMohit Khandelwal¹, Abhay Gupta², Mukesh Gupta²¹PhD Scholar, Faculty of Pharmacy, Lords University, Alwar, Rajasthan²Professor, Faculty of Pharmacy, Lords University, Alwar, Rajasthan

Received: 22-06-2023 Revised: 11-07-2023 / Accepted: 15-08-2023

Corresponding author: Mohit Khandelwal

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

The main aim of this study was to develop a topical drug delivery (Hydrogel) of Sertaconazole to reduce the dose of the active drug, to improve patient compliance, to avoid the side effects and increase local onset absorption and action. Sertaconazole interfere with 14- α sterol demethylase, a cytochrome P-450 enzyme essential for conversion of lanosterol to ergosterol. These turn in inhibition in synthesis of ergosterol and also enhance cellular permeability of fungus due to reduced amounts of ergosterol present in the fungal cell membrane.

Methods: Topical Hydrogel formulations development of Sertaconazole was prepared by using Different-different polymers by enhancer stability and viscosity with their different concentrations. Six different formulations of Sertaconazole were prepared and evaluated parameters with respect to their colour, Spreadability, viscosity, determination of pH, drug content of formulations, in vitro drug release studies, and stability studies.

Results: FT-IR study results that there were no any interaction between the drug, Polymers, and excipients. All the developed formulations of Sertaconazole show acceptable standard physical properties. The drug content and percentage yield were higher for F5 formulation among all formulation. F5 shows better drug release. Stability study of the best formulation F5 with guar gum polymer was found with best results.

Conclusion: From the above observation results that this F5 formulation may be more effective topical formulation for the healing of fungal infections in the skin.

Keywords: Sertaconazole, Hydrogel, Zeta potential, Lanosterol, Ergosterol, Cell membrane.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

A gel may be a two-component, cross linked three-dimensional network consisting of structural materials interspersed by an adequate but proportionally large amount of liquid to make an infinite rigid network structure which immobilizes the liquid continuous phase within formulation. The structural materials that form the gel network are often composed of inorganic particles or organic macromolecules, primarily polymers. Cross links are often formed via chemical or physical interactions. This results in gel classification into chemical and physical gel systems, respectively. Sertaconazole interfere with 14- α sterol demethylase, a cytochrome P-450 enzyme essential for conversion of lanosterol to ergosterol. These turn in inhibition in synthesis of ergosterol and also enhance cellular permeability of fungus due to reduced amounts of ergosterol present in the fungal cell membrane. As ergosterol is an essential component of the fungal cell membrane, inhibition of its synthesis results in the increased cellular permeability causing leakage of cellular contents responsible for cell death.[1-6]

Classification of Gels

Gels may be classified supported colloidal phases, nature of solvent used, physical nature and rheological properties.

1. Based on nature of solvent**Hydro gels (water based)**

Here they contain water as their continuous liquid phase E.g. bentonite, derivatives of cellulose, carpooler, and synthetic poloxamer gel. Example-plastibase (low molecular wt. polyethylene dissolved in oil) Olag (aerosol) gel and dispersion of metallic stearate in oils.

Hydrogel

A Hydrogel, is a semisolid formulation of gel dosage forms, which has an immobilized external apolar phase. The apolar phase is immobilized within spaces of the 3D network structure formed due to the physical interactions amongst all polymers the self-assembling structures of compounds regarded as gelators.[7]

Xerogels

Solid gels with low solvent concentration are called xerogels. These are produced by evaporation of solvent or freeze drying, leaving the gel framework behind on contact with fresh fluid, they swells and may be reconstituted. E.g. Tragacanth ribbons, acacia tear β 1-cyclodextrin, dry cellulose and polystyrene.[8]

2. Based on colloidal phases

They're classified into Inorganic (two phase system) kind of force that's accountable for the linkages determine the structure of the network and therefore the properties of the gel.[8]

Single-phase system these contain large organic molecules existing on the twisted strands dissolved during a continuous phase.

3. Based on rheological properties

Usually the gels show non-Newtonian flow properties. They're classified into, a) Plastic gels b) Pseudo plastic gels c) Thixotropic gels. (a) Plastic gels E.g. - Bingham bodies, flocculated suspensions of aluminium hydroxide exhibit a plastic flow and also the plot of rheogram gives the yield value of the gels above which the elastic gel distorts and begins to flow. (b) Pseudo-plastic gels E.g. - Liquid tragacanth dispersion, sodium alginate, Na Carboxy methyl cellulose etc. exhibits pseudo-plastic flow.[9]

4. Based on physical nature

(a) Elastic gels Gels of agar, pectin, guar gum and alginates exhibit an elastic behavior. The fibrous molecules being linked at the purpose of junction by relatively weak bonds like hydrogen bonds and dipole attraction. E.g.: Alginate and Carbapol. (b) Rigid gels this may be formed from macromolecule within which the framework linked by primary valance bond. E.g.: In colloid, silic acid molecules are held by Si-O-Si-O bond to provide a polymer structure possessing a network of pores.

Preparation of Gels

Gels are generally prepared at the industrial scale under roomtemperature. However few of polymers such-Synthetic and Natural need special treatment before processing. Gels are also prepared by following methods.[10-11]

1. Thermal changes
2. Flocculation
3. Chemical process/ reaction

Materials and Methods

Sertaconazole was received gift sample from Praise Pharma Ltd, Mumbai, India. All Other Chemicals used in the formulation development

were of the standard analytical grade. Sertaconazole formulations Hydrogel were prepared by using different polymers with their different-different concentrations. Polymers are dispersed in distilled water with constant stirring by magnetic stirrer at a medium speed maintaining the temperature at 40°C.

Gels are packed in a wide mouthed glass jar, and it is covered with screw copped plastic lid after covering with aluminium foil. Various preparations of Sertaconazole hydrogel are shown in Table 1. They all were kept in the dark and cool place. Evaluation of physicochemical parameters of prepared hydrogel of Sertaconazole gel Drug-excipients compatibility studies by Fourier transfer infrared spectrophotometer (FTIR). The drug, polymer, and excipients interactions are studied using the FTIR method. In general, drug and excipients must be compatible with each other which produce a stable, safe, and efficacious formulation. IR spectral analysis of pure drug and polymers carried out. Pure drug that gives peak and patterns were compared with the peaks and patterns with the combination of polymer and drug.[11-15]

Results and Discussion

Drug-excipients compatibility studies

The IR studies of clear Sertaconazole formulation comprises greater proportion of the polymers that are conducted to know about the bond between the used polymers and the drug.

The IR spectrum of pure Sertaconazole and Sertaconazole gel formulations that used greater proportion of polymer that gives comparable basic patterns and peaks. Outcome status that no notable drug and polymer interactions.

Visual inspection

Visual determination is done to examine the physical properties and color of the developed formulation.

Determination of pH

The pH value of all developed gel was in the range of 6.5–7.4. This is sufficient for appealing to skin and avoid the chances of irritation with local application.

Spreadability

The study has a few major elements that show the gel character that emerges out from the tube. Spreadability test is carried for all the formulations.

Determination of drug content:

The drug content of the formulated gel was estimated. The drug content manifests that the drug was distributed equally throughout the gel.

Percentage yield and viscosity

Percentage yield of a topical gel consisting of Sertaconazole was in the range of 94.15–98.55%.

This was identified that the percentage yield of F5 formulation showed an increase in percentage yield than the other preparation due to use of guar gum polymer.

In vitro drug release

The drug release profile of Sertaconazole topical gel formulations was accomplished by Franz diffusion cell. As an outcome of the *in vitro* release studies of all formulations are given in Table 3, and the statistically represented is shown in Figure.

Table 1: Hydrogel

Ingredients (mg)	DCH1	DCH2	DCH3
Sertaconazole	200mg	200mg	200mg
Carbopol	100mg	-	-
HPMC	-	100mg	-
Guar Gum	-	-	100mg
Propylene Glycol	500mg	500mg	500mg
DMSO	1ml	1ml	1ml
Triethanolamine	10mg	10mg	10mg
Methyl Paraben	10mg	10mg	10mg
Propyl Paraben	0.25mg	0.25mg	0.25mg
Water	8.1ml	8.1ml	8.1ml
Total	≈10gm	≈10gm	≈10gm

Active Drug (Sertaconazole) and all the ingredients were collected according to the formula the given above table. Dissolve 200mg Sertaconazole in 1ml of DMSO. Solution of Drug ethanol, water and Propylene glycol prepared and tagged with Beaker-A. Add 100 mg carbopol/HPMC/Guar Gum in solution-A with constant stirring at 500 rpm for about 2 hours. Propylene glycol, methyl paraben, propyl paraben and Triethanolamine were added to it with maintaining 25°C. Final weight was made with water. All the samples were allowed to equilibrate for 24 h at room temperature prior to performing evaluation test.

Standard curve of Sertaconazole

The Sertaconazole was characterized in methanol as solvent by measuring absorption spectrum using Shimadzu UV Visible Spectrophotometer. The drug exhibited λ_{max} at 272 nm when scanned between 180-400 nm.

Standard curve of Sertaconazole was obtained by plotting absorbance values at different concentrations of the drug UV- spectrophotometer. The standard plot was made with concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) on X axis and Absorbance on Y axis.

Table 2: Absorbance Sertaconazole

Concentration	Absorbance (272 nm)
0.0	0
2.0	0.123±0.002
4.0	0.258±0.003
6.0	0.388±0.001
8.0	0.525±0.002
10.0	0.651±0.003
12.0	0.789±0.001

All values are expressed as mean (\pm SD), $n = 3$

Figure 1: Calibration Curve Sertaconazole

Table 3: Characterization of formulation of Sertaconazole Gel

Characterization	Formulation code					
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
pH	7.2	7.3	6.9	7.1	7.2	7.5
Viscosity (CPS)	8791	9128	9292	9185	8753	9095
Visual Appearance	Tanslu-cent	Tanslu-cent	Tanslu-cent	Tanslu-cent	Tanslu-cent	Tanslu-cent
Gelling capacity	++	++	++	+++	++++	+++
Content	94.25	98.45	95.65	96.23	97.35	97.15
Uniformity	±0.01	±0.02	±0.01	±0.03	±0.02	±0.03

Figure 2:

Table 4: % Cumulative drug release from various batches

Time (Min.)	F1	F2	F3
0	0	0	0
5	18.44	16.23	22.34
10	26.12	25.24	21.24
15	45.22	47.23	44.28
20	74.23	80.41	81.12
30	71.21	76.16	75.15

Figure 3:

Table 5: % Cumulative drug release from various batches

Time (Min.)	F4	F5	F6
0	0	0	0
5	13.32	22.22	19.31
10	14.47	25.21	29.37
15	54.35	55.55	52.56
20	88.29	95.56	94.81
30	55.25	61.25	65.31

Figure 4:

Discussion

The imidazole derivative of Sertaconazole is one of the best drugs used for the treatment of fungal infections. In this study, the topical gel preparation of Sertaconazole was formulated for efficient that absorption of the drug across the skin. Advanced formulations of Sertaconazole were analyzed for physiochemical parameters such as viscosity, Spreadability, drug content, and *in vitro* drug release studies.

Conclusion

By analysing the above results, concluded that our drug Sertaconazole was incorporated with success into the topical gel development among all the

designed formulation, the formulation F2 shows better Spreadability, drug content, viscosity, and drug release studies.

Therefore, this was concluded that our formulation would be very effective and safe topical alternative for the treatment of skin fungal infections.

References

1. Niwano Y, Ohmi T, Seo A, Kodama H, Koga H, Sakai A. Lanoconazole and its related optically active compound nnd-502: novel anti-fungal imidazoles with a ketene dithioacetal structure. *Curr Med Chem.* 2003;2:147–160.
2. Pooja Kumari , Dr. Dilip Agrawal, Mr.

- Ashok Kumar Sharma, Mr. Mohit Khandelwal, Ms. Shaneza Aman, Ms. Shweta bhandari, An Recent Advancement In Topical Dosage Forms: A Review, International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Review and Research 2021; 13(1); 01-08.
3. Draelos ZD, Vlahovic TC, Gold MH, Parish LC, Korotzer A. A Randomized, Double-blind, Vehicle-controlled Trial of Sertaconazole Cream 1% in the Treatment of Interdigital TineaPedis. *J Clin Aesthet Dermatol.* 2014;7(10):20-27.
 4. Michaels AS, Chandrasekaran SK, Shaw JE. Drug permeation through human skin: theory and in vitro experimental measurement. *AICHE J* 1975;21:985-96.
 5. Mandal, Rakesh, Rupesh Singh, Ashok Saini, Vandana Sharma, Mukesh Sharma, Ashok Kumar Sharma, and Vani Madaan. "A Review On Anti Aging Herbal Face Cream."
 6. Sharma, Ashok Kumar, Pushpendra Singh Naruka, Shankar Lal Soni, Vani Madaan, Vandana Sharma, and Mukesh Sharma. "Amphotericin-B: A Drug Approach In Fungal Treatment.
 7. Sharma, J., Agrawal, D., Sharma, A., Khandelwal, M., & Aman, S. (2022). New Topical Drug Delivery System Pharmaceutical Organogel: A Review. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Development*, 10(1), 75-78.
 8. Sharma, V., Sharma, M., Sharma, A.K., Mandal, R.S.R., Saini, A. And Shariq, M., 2021. Anti Aging Therapy By Herbal Cream: A REVIEW. *DICKENSIAN*, 21(12).
 9. cauley WJ, Caserta F, Hoboken NJ. Film-forming and heated systems. In: Donnelly RF, Singh TRR. editors. *Novel delivery systems for transdermal and intradermal drug delivery*. United States: John Wiley and Sons; 2015. p. 97-107.
 10. Frederiksen K, Guy RH, Petersson K. The potential of polymeric film-forming systems as sustained delivery platforms for topical drugs. *Expert Opin Drug Delivery* 2015; 13:349-60.
 11. B.V. Mikari, K.R.Mahadik, Formulation and evaluation of topical liposomal gel for fluconazole. *S.A. Korde, Indian J .Pharm.Sci.*, 2010. 44(4), 324-325.
 12. Dodov Glavas-Dodov, 5-Fluorouracil in topical liposome gels for anticancer treatment- formulation and evaluation, *Maja Simonoska, Act a pharm*, 2003 (53), 241-250.
 13. Rupal Jani, Kaushal Jani, Setty C.Mallikarjuna, Preparation and evaluation of topical gel Valdecocib. *Dipti Patel, Inter.journal.Pharm.Sci.Research.* 2010, 2(1), 51-54.
 14. Sharma A K, Naruka P S, Soni S, Sarangdewot YS, Khandelwal M, Shaneza A, Formulation, Development And Evaluation of Luliconazole Hydrogel; *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Review and Research.*, Nov. 2018, 10(4), Pages: 01-06.